

The Essence of Economic Tasks in the Implementation of Economic Relations of the Family

Nigora Lutfullaeva¹, Dilorom Doniyarovna Ergasheva²

¹Associate Professor, Tashkent State University of Economics

²Senior teacher, Tashkent State University of Economics

ABSTRACT: In this article, the authors focused on the analysis of the economic function of the family, which are the priority areas of today's economic reforms, the causes of income in the family, the main features of the family and household, the composition of their functions, as well as the concept of economic relations of family students.

KEYWORDS: Cost, Consumer, Economy, Economic Relations, Family, Household, Income, Reforms.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of deepening integration processes in the world, global changes in social relations have a significant impact on the institution of the family, its status, structure, composition, functions and activities. It is also necessary to improve the institutional framework for ensuring the interests of the family in a new context, as the approaches to family and family relations are changing dramatically in many developing countries on the basis of social, political and economic reforms. Therefore, the scientific study of family-marriage traditions, family relations and family functions, the scientific study of their social, psychological, economic aspects, which have not yet been well analyzed, is of great importance.

ANALYSIS OF THE RELEVANT LITERATURE

Within the framework of the socio-psychological perspective of family relations, a number of research works have been carried out, some aspects of which are discussed by domestic scientists: A.Soginov, E.N.Sattarov, U.Qodirov, B.M.Umarov, R.S. Samarov, F.A.Akramova Z.A.Rasulova, M.Fayziyeva, G.T.Yadgarova, M.Utepbergenov, F. Ruzikulov, K.Abdurahmanov, A.Olmasov, A.Vahobov, Sh.Shodmonov, U. Gafurov, A.Rasulev, D.Tadjibayeva expressed their views.

CIS researchers A.N.Antonov, T.V.Andreeva, A.G.Kharchev, E.P.Belinskaya, Z.Z.Vakhitova, A.P.Vyatkin, E.V.Golubeva, A.I.Gochiyayev, N.A.Juravleva, E.A.Ug-lanova, N.V.Mojaykina and the scientific work of others focuses on economic relations in the family.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In educational institutions during this study perceptions of family students about household based on a socio-psychological surveys systematic approach and analytical methods were used.

The theoretical and methodological basis of this article is the literature and scientific articles on family relationships of family students, the analysis of the views of scholars, the observation of the process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The family is a small group of people who meet the social, spiritual, spiritual and economic needs of individuals connected by kinship and relationship. The family tries to meet their needs as much as possible and fulfills it. It is the owner of the factors of production, at least the factor of labor, that ensures the reproduction of 'human capital'. In real life, a family can also consist of a single self-employed person¹.

The family's responsibilities to society are understood, first of all, its ability to meet the specific needs of family members and thereby serve the needs and interests of the state and society. For example, when a father works in a manufacturing company

¹Sarsenbaeva R.M. Ways of forming economic education in the family. Modern education .2017.5

from morning till night, he not only satisfies his needs for food, rest and various purchases, but also meets the needs of family members, especially children, housewives, and spouses. The increase in profitability of this or that enterprise contributes to the high economic performance, and thus to the development of this industry in their homeland.²

The economic function of the family is one of its main functions. The family economy, budget, planned spending of income, allocation of money for daily expenses, necessary items, saving for a few years, saving money depend on the couple's great experience and skills. It is also important to teach the child to solve economic problems, keeping in mind that the child growing up in the family must also have these skills and abilities. In recent years, economic problems in families have negatively affected interpersonal relationships in the family, leading to a decline in children's education. In order to prevent such unpleasant situations, it is necessary to provide psychological assistance to people in overcoming the problems that arise due to financial difficulties. Due to this task, the family brings great economic benefits to society and the state. For example, the benefits that a child's upbringing brings to society in terms of the child's economic well-being are enormous. This is done by the state, in public institutions (orphanages) to raise a child for 16-18 years and raise him as a labor force (feeding, dressing, educating, providing materially, etc.) the money spent by the state on each child and exactly the same worker if we compare the amount of alimony paid for the upbringing of his family, the difference between them is several hundred thousand sums in favor of the former. To make it easier to imagine, it can be said that for the upbringing of each child, the family brings to the state an economic benefit of at least ten to fifteen million sums. In this regard, that is, the spiritual and moral aspects of the development of a comprehensively developed spiritually and morally mature, physically and psychologically healthy person cannot be measured by any economic criteria. This only shows the value of the economic function of the family in shaping the individual. The growth of economic activity in the modern family, the organization of work, the production of material goods, farming, personal production, etc., shows that the importance of its economic function to society is growing.

Based on the priorities of today's economic reforms, the functions of the family economy include the following socio-economic measures:

- educating the younger generation and reproducing the labor force;
- meeting the consumption needs of the family;
- family business activities (in agriculture, home-based industry and especially in the service sector);
- creation of investment opportunities at the expense of the family fund, effective use of property income;
- "domestic" economic relations with the state (payment of taxes, use of transfer payments), economic relations with foreign countries, in particular, the conclusion of various remittances and employment contracts. From this it can be concluded that the functions of the household are interrelated, all of which involve a certain amount of income and expenses. This process is not limited to the family economy, but also manifests itself as a process that takes place in the whole system of economic relations³.

Within the family, each party undertakes to perform certain tasks. In almost all nations, women have traditionally been responsible for household chores, while men have been responsible for providing for the family. Current developments also have an impact on this traditional division of labor and each family seeks to address it based on the characteristics of the couple. In the family, both parties are interested in creating family activists and creating a solid material base. The family is a unique investment project aimed at achieving a certain result after a few years. In this respect, it can be compared to a specific business, investment. The family, that is, the household, performs extremely complex economic tasks. He is a family business owner, a creator of the labor force, ie an investor in human capital. is a subject that creates the necessary level of consumer demand and fulfills others and in the process the family solves many problems. The creation of a material basis in the family is that the household is run and the family income is formed. In Uzbekistan, this process is often carried out not independently, but with the support of parents. Parents think of their child, thankfully help and support. The fact that a newly married family often relies on parental support, both materially and spiritually, on the one hand, helps to solve the problems that arise from the inexperience of the new family. At the same time, the current economic process of the family is associated with running a house-hold, creating goods and services, family business, ie

²V.M.Karimova. Family Psychology: Textbook. For students of pedagogical universities // - T.: "Science and technology", 2008. - 170 p.

³Sh.O. Quvandikov. Family business: its role, importance and development factors in the national economy. Scientific electronic journal "Economy and Innovative Technologies". № 1, January-February, 2014

the organization of individual production as a property owner, private entrepreneurship, small business, organizes and operates family businesses, farms and dehqan farms, and generates family income. The family income (fund) will become an economic reserve fund, and a stabilization fund will be established.

The reasons for family income are as follows:

1. To buy something that will cost a lot of money in the future. Family members make current expenses almost every day. The income received is not all spent in one day. A certain part of it is stored for a month (in cash or on a credit card), a number of things are difficult to buy for a month's earned income, so you need to save money.

2. Against all odds (insurance). Family members are always thinking about the future. They may have to earn less in the future or incur additional costs. Or there may be situations where you have to spend money in unexpected situations.

3. To make a profit. The desire to earn an active, additional income that generates income is an important incentive to save. The fund can be in the following forms:

- first, in the form of cash; the reason is that its liquidity is the highest, but its biggest drawback is that it depreciates due to inflation. This is why family members often try to keep their money in reliable foreign currencies. If inflation is not strong and the money is accumulating for something to be bought soon, it will be kept in the national currency.

- secondly, in the form of expensive real estate, antiques (housing, etc), expensive jewelry: they at least retain their nominal value or the price rises. They need to be stored, and storage requires additional costs. Liquidity is low, making it difficult to convert to cash quickly.

-thirdly, to try to capitalize, to start your own business. Here, the emergence of the financial market or banks and other financial institutions will create new opportunities to increase personal savings, earn income. But behind the high return, the risk is also high. In a market economy, there are many different ways to save. If you need to save money in old age, you can buy a pension fund, life insurance against various events, any type of securities.

It is sometimes said that the economy of the family is related to the word household, so in the literature in most cases the term 'household' is combined with the concept of 'family' or has a complementary or even substitutive relationship.

Vinter M. and Morris U. in research⁴ it is recognized that "a family is a group that does not have to live in the same house and have a common budget, but is united by the generality of family and kinship ties". Urumova F.I. "The family is a subgroup of people, usually consciously organized on the basis of kinship and common life, whose life and activities are carried out to meet the social, economic and spiritual needs of the individual."⁵ he pointed out. It is clear from these definitions that characteristics such as kinship, marriage, and the provision of social functions are essential for the family, but they are not sufficient to recognize the family as a household. Household is also characterized by key characteristics such as cohabitation, co-management, shared budget, and marital-kinship ties (Table 1). There may or may not be marital-kinship ties. However, this allows us to conclude that the distinctive features of "household" and "family" often coincide, but the family is the basis of the household. To see this more clearly, it is possible to compare the main features and structural-functional characteristics of the family with the household (Table 1).

The structure of the main features and functions of the family and the household

Functions	Family	Household
1	2	3
Key characters (written according to importance)	Marriage and kinship; place of residence; general budget; joint venture	Place of residence; joint management; general budget; marriage-kinship relations
The main goal	Bringing man into the world	Preservation and restoration of human capital
Specific functions arising from the nature of the family and the household	The birth of a child, his upbringing and development, the performance of social functions - remain	Supply, production, consumption accumulation - is the basis for the restoration and implementation of human

⁴Mojaykina N.V. Sotsialno - ekonomicheskaya sushchnost category domoxozyaystva. //http/www.nbuuv.gov.

⁵Absamatov A. Issues of agricultural development in the region. // Economic Bulletin of Uzbekistan. - T., 2000. 4-son.

	unchanged at all stages of development of society.	capital, reflects the historical nature of external and internal economic relations
Mandatory or customized non-specific functions in a particular historical context	Household; production; consumption; renewal and other functions - reflect the historical nature of family relationships and the family's interaction with society	Child rearing and other social functions are aimed at creating, shaping and maintaining the physiological basis of human potential

The results of a comparative analysis of the main functions of the household and the family show that they are complementary and interdependent, that is, the successful implementation of specific household functions (supply, production, accumulation and consumption) are simultaneously family specific functions and depends on the quality, storage and implementation of its non-specific functions. This allows us to draw the following conclusions by supplementing the main functions of households, dividing them into specific and non-specific types. The concept of the restoration of human capital, reflecting more deeply the essence of the multifaceted process, not only rehabilitates the individual as an individual and the household as a community, both biologically and socially, but also economically. but also to create the conditions for his life and activity. This concept reflects the sum of the material, human, spiritual, ethnic, religious foundations of the existence of the household, and this shows its versatility and great importance. But in terms of its economic value, the household is often seen as a conservation of human capital⁶. The structure of the household differs from each other in the following respects:

- a form of single person, living in a separate house or part of it, independently meeting all the needs for life and not a common means of economic management with other people living together;
- two or more persons, living separately - living together or separately on the spot, satisfying their general needs by combining or separating all or part of their means in the general activities of daily life. These individuals may be connected through marriage, tribal-kinship ties or even non-kinship ties. The household may also include persons who are strangers to its members, but who live in the same place and are the sole breadwinners (elderly and other persons living under the auspices of the household).

In cases where the building is leased, the owner of the building is not considered a member of the established household. At the same time, domestic workers are not considered members of the household even when they live in their employers' homes (provided with shelter and food for their labor).

So, although the concepts of "household" and "family" are similar, as noted above, the family is the core of the household. A person can be a household, but not a family. A household can be made up of a large number of people, but they are not always connected by kinship ties. In-depth understanding of the concept of household in turn helps to understand the difference between running a household economy. Household activities are carried out at home with the participation of its members as a labor force. Accommodation includes keeping the place and the surrounding area in good condition, cooking, caring for children and the disabled, and more. Household activities are not limited to household chores.

It is also a creative subject of the market economy, in which the family member has the freedom of choice in the implementation of the household as an "economic man" and can make optimal and rational decisions based on their goals, interests and needs.⁷ Serves, operates and interacts with society through its economic consciousness and behavior. It should be noted that economic consciousness is the emotions, feelings arising from economic relations, the elements of perspective perception related to the understanding of their various aspects, the knowledge, concepts, ideas, skills, etc. the intellectual properties of skills are understood. It arises from the direct influence of economic situations and conditions on the consciousness, worldview and motives of the individual, and is based on the performance of economic roles - consumer, buyer, seller.

Enriched with economic understanding and information, his consciousness and behavior lead him to engage in activities based on economic culture. As a result, the economic function of the family is fully fulfilled, and the well-being of the family continues to develop in harmony. In particular, 58.3% of family students with 68 higher education, 54.5% male and 45.5% female,

⁶U.Q. Akhmedov. Socio-economic significance of the concept of household and its integral connection with the family. Scientific electronic journal "Economy and Innovative Technologies". № 6, November-December, 2016

⁷G.M.Gukasyan. Economics from "A" to "Ya". Thematic directory. M. 2010

were surveyed and asked “What do you mean by household management” when planning and analyzing the financial situation of the family; 50% equal distribution of homework among its members; 47.4% said they would find a single solution to major procurement and economic issues.

“Who taught you to run a household?” to the question, 100% of respondents said they were parents, 58.3% said they had learned from life experience, and 33.3% said they had read from books. 8.3% responded by saying that they were taught in special courses.

“Who runs the household in your family?” 66.7% of participants reported male, 25% mixed, and 8.3% maternal.

58.3% of respondents “How interested are you in the processes of our economy?” marked as average to the question. “How often do you watch media coverage of our country’s economic policy?” and when we said that, 50% answered sometimes, 50% often.

When we asked them to “set the most important values for you”, 100% of the respondents agreed that the most important values are family, and 83.3% - health and education.

On the question of family environment and stability, 89% of respondents admitted its existence. This situation is characterized by the fact that for family students, all life aspirations are focused on family issues, self-awareness. They also show that the family has formed an understanding of the household and has information about the economic responsibilities of the family. The great role of parents in all relations in Uzbek families means that they are also important in managing economic issues. At the same time, with the help of various media, meaningful videos covering various aspects of the state economy, broadcasts promoting the economic functions of the family.

CONCLUSIONS

The family is a combination of the interests of the couple and the children in the home, giving a general direction to their efforts. Therefore, there are a number of principles of housekeeping that need to be followed. For example:

The first principle is that the behavior of the family is required to be subordinated to meet the needs of all family members.

The second principle is that the decision on the economic activity of the family should be made on a democratic basis. If this decision is made and implemented by an individual member of the family, then it is also required to guarantee the interests of other family members.

The third principle is that the family should follow the principle of economic rationalism, that is, the family should follow the most conscious, self-sufficient way to increase their well-being.

The fourth principle is to follow the rule of alternative choice. The family will have a lot of needs, but the income it earns will be limited and will not be able to meet all the needs. Therefore, the most essential needs will have to be selected and they will be met at low cost.

The fifth principle is to follow the rule of economic compromise. This requires family members to decide who will do what to improve the well-being of the family, when to meet their individual needs, and to do it together. The compromise in the family can be resolved by the elders of the house (father, mother, father-in-law, mother-in-law, brother, sisters).

The sixth principle is to plan family income and expenses, ensuring their compatibility and avoiding a deficit in the family budget. These principles are aimed at ensuring that the family is harmonious and harmonious, that family life is consistently good.

Based on the above information, we can say that in the process of preparing young people for family life, not only social psychological but also economic knowledge is important, in this regard, it is advisable to carry out systematic work in the family, education system, additional programs.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.Mirziyoev. Resolution No. PQ-55 of December 20, 2021 “On additional measures for the development of family business and expanding the source of income of the population”.
2. V.M.Karimova. Family Psychology: Textbook. For students of pedagogical universities // - T.: “Science and technology”, 2008. - 170 p.
3. Andreeva T.V. Semeynaya psychology. - SPb.: 2004 ..
4. Baker K. Theory semeynyx system M. Bouena // Voprosy psichologii. 1991. №6.

5. Sh.O. Quvandikov. Family business: its role, importance and development factors in the national economy. Scientific electronic journal "Economy and Innovative Technologies". № 1, January-February, 2014.
6. Mojaykina N.V. Sotsialno - ekonomicheskaya sushchnost category domoxoz-yaystva.
7. Absamatov A. Issues of agricultural development in the region. // Economic Bulletin of Uzbekistan. - T., 2000. 4-son.
8. U.Q. Akhmedov. Socio-economic significance of the concept of household and its integral connection with the family. Scientific electronic journal "Economy and Innovative Technologies". № 6, November-December, 2016
9. Sarsenbaeva R. Ways of forming economic education in the family. Modern education. 2017
10. G.M.Gukasyan. Economics from "A" to "Ya". Thematic directory. M. 2010

Cite this Article: Nigora Lutfullaeva, Dilorom Doniyarovna Ergasheva (2022). The Essence of Economic Tasks in the Implementation of Economic Relations of the Family. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(4), 997-1002